

Age nodes derived from horizontal fission tracks

Peter Klint Jensen*

*Technical University of Denmark, Anker Engelunds Vej 101, Kgs. Lyngby, pkkje@dtu.dk

The apparent fission track age equation is designed to calculate the age of fast cooling apatites from temperatures above 120 °C to below 60 °C. Nevertheless, the equation is widely used even when the cooling rate is moderate. Age dating is refined by simulation of fission track length histograms with application of track length annealing models. Age nodes can now be extracted after laborious computations. In practice the age nodes given by the fission tracks are masked by the variance of the temperature history and the introduction of prior information.

Alternatively, age nodes can be calculated directly without the use of annealing models. Keil et al. (1987) suggested to age date a given fully included randomly oriented unetched track by counting the number of shorter tracks in a volume and divide by the track generation rate. In practice the tracks are etched to make them visible in the light microscope and only nearly horizontal fully included tracks are selected for analysis. So, age equations were developed providing direct calculation of ages with standard deviations for each mean track length histogram (Jensen et al., 1992; Jensen and Hansen, 2021). It is considered that present tracks, generated simultaneously, are spread out over an interval of lengths after annealing. It is therefore questionable whether a short track is older than a longer track. The problem is mitigated by mathematical deconvolution in which the track length spreading is diminished. This is done by application of the track length spreading measured in laboratory annealing experiments. Deconvolution is performed using the least squares principle combined with probabilistic inverse theory (Tarantola, 2005) which leads to direct calculation of ages with deviations related to mean track lengths.

Blurring of track lengths is traditionally mitigated by projection of track lengths to the c-axis (Donelick et al., 1999). An example of further deblurring using deconvolution is illustrated here. Track length blurring seen in laboratory annealing experiments are used in the process.

As an example, a c-axis projected track length histogram (GRÖ64) from Greenland (Spiegel et al., 2023) is deblurred and converted to time intervals. The figure shows the derived time intervals (green bars). The black points show the cumulated ages of the oldest track in each time interval. It is seen that the oldest deconvolved track is of length 10 μm with the expected age 193 ± 16 Ma. The tracks of length 10-12 μm are generated at relatively elevated temperatures in a period lasting 95 Ma. A rapid transition of duration 29 Ma to lower temperatures is shown by the tracks from 12-13 μm. A period of lower temperatures lasting 67 Ma led to the track lengths 13-15 μm. The GRÖ64 histogram supports 2-3 age nodes when taking the age standard deviations into account.

The least squares principle may result in unrealistically inverted negative deconvolved track length histogram columns. Implementation of positive prior values with sufficient weight minimizes the problem.

Deblurring fission track length histograms provide information on the number of age nodes that can be extracted from each histogram. The age of each node is given with standard deviation. The age nodes may be used to identify post-sedimentary tracks and may guide the selection of prior information used in thermal history modelling.